

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan)

Geolinguistics and Sino-Tibetan: An introduction

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Abstract: Geolinguistics is expected to contribute to the diachronic study of the Sino-Tibetan language family, which typologically shows significant diversity across regions. This article introduces concepts, methods, and recent results of geolinguistic study. We also survey the differences between geolinguistics and the adjacent fields of study, including areal linguistics.*

Keywords: geolinguistics; language geography; areal linguistics; linguistic map; Sino-Tibetan

1. Overview of the geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan

The Sino-Tibetan languages show remarkable diversity and regional distribution of their typological characteristics (cf. the concept of spheres in Matisoff 1990, 1991, 2003, 2021). In this feature, “Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan,” we present the method of geolinguistics as an approach to the diversity of Sino-Tibetan languages and provide practical examples of research.

Figure 1 presents an example from Endo et al. eds. (2021: Map 7), a linguistic map produced by the geolinguistic method, to which I have added borderlines and annotations. The red circle corresponds to the boundary between the inner and outer groups defined by Iwata (2021). This figure visually illustrates a hypothesis of tone diffusion from southern China; to the east and west of the syllabic tone language region lie word tone regions, and further out are the distinctive pitch-accented regions (cf.

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Hayata 1999, Matisoff 2001). The Sinitic languages fall within the tonal area, whereas the Tibeto-Burman languages are found in all the tonal, intermediate (with word tones), and atonal (outside the circles) areas. This geographical distribution suggests that, from a macro perspective, the tone systems among the Tibeto-Burman languages are innovations.

Sinitic

The number of phonological tones

- ★ 1
- ☆ 2
- 3
- 4
- | 5
- 6

Tibeto-Burman

- | | |
|------------|---------------|
| □ WT+NP | ⊞ WT+SA+NP |
| ○ ST+NP | ▣ WT+YT |
| ◐ ST+YL | ⊞ NT/NA+ST+YL |
| — NT/NA+NP | ⊞ PA+ST+YT |
| △ RG+YC | ⊞ ST+SA+NP |
| ⊞ ST+YT | ⊞ ST+SA+YL |
| ⊞ NT/NA+YC | ⊞ WT+RG+YC |
| ⊞ PA+NP | |

Fig. 1: Tone and accent in Sino-Tibetan and adjacent languages (Excerpted from Endo et al. 2021: Map 7. Boundaries, arrows, and annotations in the map were added by the author for illustrative purposes.)¹

¹ Abbreviations in the Tibeto-Burman Map Legend: NP: no phonation pattern, NT/NA: no tone or accent, PA: pitch accent, RG: register, SA: stress accent, ST: syllabic tone, WT: word tone, YC: phonation influenced by initial consonants, YL: distinctive phonation, YT: phonetic phonation.

We consider that a geolinguistic approach could be effective in studying the Sino-Tibetan language family. This introductory paper is followed by three related specific studies: Ebihara and Saitô (this volume) discuss the interactions between Tibetic and Mongolic languages belonging to different language families. Then, H. Suzuki, Yagi, and F. Suzuki (this volume) examine the distribution of word forms within the Sino-Tibetan language family, using examples from animal and plant terms. Finally, Iwasa (this volume) provides a unique study of Yi characters using diverse regional manuscripts, which are mutually almost incomprehensible. Each study was conducted from a different perspective, but they all demonstrate the validity of a geolinguistic approach.

2. Basic concepts

2.1. Philosophies of linguistic geography

Geolinguistic methods are based on those of linguistic geography (or dialect geography). This section outlines the basic concepts of linguistic geography, mainly based on Sibata (1969). This paper distinguishes geolinguistics and linguistic geography, and their differences are explained in Section 2.3.

“Every word has a history.” This epigram is attributed to Jules Gilliéron, a Swiss-French dialectologist of the 19th and early 20th centuries. Sibata (1969: 16–19) cited these words and added, “Language systems do not change at once. When dealing with individual and personal phenomena, even members of the same community do not necessarily have the same language. However, when dealing with the geographic distribution, we can find orderliness in it because it is a projection of history.” He clearly identified the purpose of geolinguistics as uncovering the history of a language (Sibata 1969: 11–12). These are also the basic assumptions of our work. More recently, Onishi (2016: 185) claimed that geolinguistic study should not be limited to historical facts, as it can reveal various aspects of dialects that can be studied in relation to geographic distribution. This can be understood as an expansion of linguistic geography.

2.2. Basic method of geolinguistics

The basic procedures of geolinguistic studies are common to linguistic geographical studies as outlined by Sibata (1969: 11), as cited below:

1. Select a certain linguistic part to be examined.
2. Identify the regional variants of the linguistic form that denote it.
3. Map the regional variants.
4. Identify the geographic distribution on the map.

5. Focusing on that distribution, along with other clues, estimate diachronic change and its factors.

Sibata (1969) places particular emphasis on the fourth of these steps: finding the geographic distribution: “Simply filling in a map with regional variants does not automatically produce their geographic distribution” (Sibata 1969: 12). Therefore, it is necessary to find the classification significantly distributed for historical composition through the examination of various classifications of the target linguistic phenomena (ibid.).

2.3. Difference among adjacent research areas

Geolinguistics adopts the abovementioned methods to identify the history of multiple languages using a certain linguistic feature, mainly in relation to its geographical distribution (Endo 2015). Here, we survey the differences between geolinguistics and the adjacent fields of study: linguistic geography, areal linguistics, and typological feature maps. Sibata (1969: 11–16) also made comparison with other fields, including comparative linguistics.

Linguistic geography, also referred to as dialect geography, shares common methods with geolinguistics, but its targets are slightly different: it aims to examine the history of a language (or languages in a country) based on the geographical distribution of word forms of vocabulary items. An example of this in the earliest stages is Gilliéron (1918), and Iwata ed. (2009) is an example of recent studies.

The main purpose of areal linguistics is to investigate linguistic features shared across a certain linguistic area. The historical process of their formation may be within the range of study. In this case, it seems like a geolinguistic study, but areal linguistics does not necessarily discuss detailed geographic distribution. Examples of this include Aikhenvald and Dixon eds. (2001) and Hickey ed. (2017).

Typological feature maps like those found in the *World Atlas of Language Structure* (Dryer and Haspelmath eds. 2013) only map certain typological features. Finding distributions or examining the process of formation of a distribution does not fall within the scope of their research. Hence, the research attitudes of geolinguistics and typological feature maps are very different.

3. Results of recent geolinguistic projects in Japan

Our articles form part of the result of joint research projects at the Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa (ILCAA), “Studies in Asian Geolinguistics” and “Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics,” both headed by

Mitsuaki Endo. These projects were completed in March 2023 and have resulted in a number of publications. *Studies in Asian Geolinguistics* series (eight volumes), *Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics* (two volumes), and a monograph series were published online by ILCAA and are available at <https://publication.aa-ken.jp/>. In addition, the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia* (Endo et al. eds. 2021) was published by Hituzi Syobo.

The Geolinguistic Society of Japan (GSJ) was founded in April 2019, and it continues to publish the journal *Studies in Geolinguistics* and Monograph series, including the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa* series. All publications of the GSJ are available online.

4. Summary

Geolinguistics not only maps linguistic features but also examines their distribution and history. Geolinguistics can synthesize a variety of clues to identify a history that is not visible to comparative linguistics cannot. Although comparative linguistics is an extremely sophisticated research method, the history of a language can be shown by using the findings of geolinguistics in a complementary way as well. Geolinguistics is expected to play a significant role in the diachronic study of Sino-Tibetan.

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